

Remdesivir as a choice of treatment of COVID-19: An Indian perspective

Abhirup Jain MD¹

¹Department of Medicine,
NNR Hospital, Karnataka,
India

Correspondence

Dr. Abhirup Jain, MD,
Department of Medicine, NNR
Hospital, Karnataka, India.
Email: abhirup.jain@hotmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15 June 2020
Accepted: 28 June 2020
Published: 30 June 2020

Dear Sir,

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) stormed human mankind and today, we are at war against an unprecedented pandemic of COVID-19, a highly contagious disease caused by a novel severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) coronavirus-2. In the first 6 months of the pandemic, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has spread globally infecting nearly 17 million people. COVID-19, the disease caused by SARS-CoV-2, resulted in more than 100 000 deaths in the United States and more than 730 000 worldwide. Many infected people are asymptomatic or experience mild symptoms and recover without medical intervention. However, older people and those with comorbid hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and heart disease are at higher risk of life-threatening illness.

Remdesivir (GS-5734), an inhibitor of the viral RNA-dependent, RNA polymerase with in vitro inhibitory activity against SARS-CoV-1 and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS-CoV), was identified early as a promising therapeutic candidate for COVID-19 because of its ability to inhibit SARS-CoV-2 in vitro. In addition, in nonhuman primate studies, remdesivir initiated 12 hours after inoculation with MERS-CoV reduced lung virus levels and lung damage. [1-3].

A first randomized, placebo-controlled trial of remdesivir among patients with COVID-19 conducted in Wuhan, China, could not complete enrollment to meaningfully assess efficacy. However, in a larger randomized, double-blind clinical trial, patients with severe COVID-19 treated with a 10-day course of remdesivir had a significantly shorter time to recovery than those receiving placebo (11 days vs 15 days). Subsequently, a randomized, open-label trial showed that patients with severe COVID-19 with relative hypoxia or requiring oxygen support but not requiring ventilatory support had outcomes with 5- and 10-day courses of remdesivir that were not significantly different. [4-5] The Drug Controller General of India (DCGI) approved remdesivir lyophilised powder for emergency use in patients hospitalised with severe COVID-19.

The drug has been approved for the treatment of suspected or laboratory confirmed incidences of COVID-19 in adults and children hospitalised with severe symptoms. It will be launched in India under the brand name DESREM™ and will be available to patients in July at a price of INR 4,800. This price is a fifth of what the product will cost governments in the developed world.

KEYWORDS

COVID-19, development, phase, Remdesivir, trials, vaccine

This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)) License, which permits copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format, remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially. © 2020 The Authors. Medical Science is published by CMRA.

In India, despite all the proactive measures by central and state governments such as lockdown and social distancing, the COVID-19-positive cases continue to increase. Hence, with recent positive development with remdesivir, we need to be ready with measures to make sure the availability of remdesivir to such a huge population at affordable price.

In India, remdesivir as a new drug must undergo clinical trial before getting marketing approval. However, if it gets approved by the US-FDA, according to the Clinical Trial Rules-2019, DCGI reserves the right to issue local clinical trial waiver in special circumstances with a close watch on its safety. Recently, two Indian pharmaceutical companies, Cipla and Hetero Labs Ltd., have sought clinical trial waiver from DCGI. However, the policy of compassionate use of drugs in India is also being developed. ICMR, AIIMS, CDSCO, and other stakeholders already had three rounds of brain storming sessions.

To conclude, looking at the disease that killed more than 3 lakhs people and US-FDA has given emergency use authorization based on preliminary results showing it superior to placebo, remdesivir seems to be strong candidate. Further, results of ongoing trial will provide much needed clarity in near future. Meanwhile, India has to plan accordingly focusing on its availability, affordability, and safety for Indian population, till then we should use what best we have.

FUNDING

No funding was available for this research.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

All data and materials are included in the manuscript, no separate data is available.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Ethical approval is not required.

COMPETING INTERESTS

None declared.

PUBLISHER'S NOTE

CMRA remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. The publisher shall not be legally responsible for any types of loss, actions, claims, proceedings, demand or costs or damages whatsoever or howsoever caused arising directly or indirectly in connection with or arising out of the use of this material.

REFERENCES

1. Sheahan TP, Sims AC, Leist SR, Schäfer A, Won J, Brown AJ, et al. Comparative therapeutic

efficacy of remdesivir and combination lopinavir, ritonavir, and interferon beta against MERS-CoV. *Nat Commun* [Internet]. 2020 Jan 10;11(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13940-6>

2. Agostini ML, Andres EL, Sims AC, Graham RL, Sheahan TP, Lu X, et al. Coronavirus Susceptibility to the Antiviral Remdesivir (GS-5734) Is Mediated by the Viral Polymerase and the Proofreading Exoribonuclease. Subbarao K, editor. *mBio* [Internet]. 2018 Mar 6;9(2). <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00221-18>
3. de Wit E, Feldmann F, Cronin J, Jordan R, Okumura A, Thomas T, et al. Prophylactic and therapeutic remdesivir (GS-5734) treatment in the rhesus macaque model of MERS-CoV infection. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* [Internet]. 2020 Feb 13;117(12):6771–6. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1922083117>
Cummings MJ, Baldwin MR, Abrams D, Jacobson SD, Meyer BJ, Balough EM, et al. Epidemiology, clinical course, and outcomes of critically ill adults with COVID-19 in New York City: a prospective cohort study. *The Lancet* [Internet]. 2020 Jun;395(10239):1763–70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)31189-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31189-2)
4. Beigel JH, Tomashek KM, Dodd LE, et al; ACTT-1 Study Group Members. Remdesivir for the treatment of COVID-19-preliminary report. *N Engl J Med*. Published online May 22, 2020.